

Review Article

Rheumatoid arthritis: in past, present and future scenario

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is characterized by joint inflammation and swelling, rheumatoid factor (RF) and anticitrullinated protein antibody (ACPA) production, and bone and cartilage destruction. Drug Trend Report spending on rheumatologics grew 69 percent in the pediatric population in 2004, indicating that children are treated with biotech drugs at an increasing rate. Recent studies indicate that early and aggressive therapy, including the use of specialty biotech drugs, can improve outcomes for children with JRA. Patients with RA ultimately require DMARD therapy but adequate analgesia is also important. Paracetamol remains the analgesic of choice given its excellent safety profile and is prescribed in regular divided doses to a maximum of 4 g/day. Alone, however, it may provide. Tofacitinib (formerly tasocitinib) was recommended for approval by the Arthritis Advisory Committee to the FDA in May 2012. If approved, this will be the first RA treatment in a new class of medications known as Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors insufficient pain relief. Finally, the future will also see the increasing application of gene therapy as a front-line defense against the disease, aiming at long-term corrective treatment.

Keywords: Rheumatologics, Rheumatoid factor, Bone and cartilage destruction

Introduction

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic, systemic inflammatory disease of unknown etiology that affects 0.5-1.0% of the general population.¹ Although heterogeneous, RA is primarily characterized by symmetric, erosive synovitis, which, if uncontrolled, can lead to joint and cartilage damage, multiple co-morbidities, significant disability, and reduction in quality of life.^{2,3}

The word arthritis literally means inflammation of the joint. Inflammation is a medical term meaning pain, stiffness, redness, and swelling. RA has significant progressive morbidity, many

extra-articular complications, higher mortality rates than the general population, and considerable socioeconomic costs.⁴⁻⁶ The disease is estimated to affect up to 1% of adults in developed countries including the United States.^{7,8} RA is characterized by joint inflammation and swelling, rheumatoid factor (RF) and anticitrullinated protein antibody (ACPA) production, and bone and cartilage destruction.

Initially RA was treated reactively, focusing on prevention of the progression of symptoms and an attempt to retain functionality. With the advent of biologic therapy, progression of the disease has been slowed, but no cure has been

found and sometimes only partial disease-modifying response is achieved.⁷ RA is characterised by persistent synovitis, systemic inflammation, and auto antibodies (particularly to rheumatoid factor and citrullinated peptide).⁸

Figure 1: Joint representation. (a) Normal joint, (b) joint affected by RA.

Synovitis is driven by cytokines, which are involved in every stage of the pathogenesis of RA. The fact that the interactions of the cytokines in the inflammatory cascade are so complex explains why clinical response can vary significantly and result in partial response or failure.⁹

RA affects approximately 3 million American adults¹⁰ and occurs 2 to 3 times more frequently in women than in men.¹¹ More than half of those with RA are undiagnosed or untreated.¹²

Although disease onset is usually in middle age or later and frequency increases with age, JRA may occur in children and young adults. According to¹³ Drug Trend Report, spending on rheumatologics grew 69 percent in the pediatric population in 2004, indicating that children are treated with biotech drugs at an increasing rate. Recent studies indicate that early and aggressive therapy, including the use of specialty biotech drugs, can improve outcomes for children with JRA.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Several studies have demonstrated that biologic agents in combination with conventional disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs), such as methotrexate (MTX), significantly reduce clinical symptoms, slow or arrest erosive changes, and allow for disease remission.¹⁷⁻¹⁹

RA has a prevalence of 1% and occurs in twice as many women as it does men.²⁰ Its aetiology

remains unknown but a model whereby repeated exposure to environmental agents is coupled with a genetic predisposition to autoimmune responses seems reasonable. The most well established genetic link is with HLA-DR4.²¹ Systemic features may be associated with a poor prognosis, especially vasculitis, amyloidosis and pulmonary fibrosis.²²

There is some evidence that the inheritability of RA appears to be high, with the genetic contribution to susceptibility estimated to be around 60%.²³ Environmental factors appear to play an important but uncertain role. Some studies have shown that the risk of developing RA is higher among smokers,²⁴ with a 2006 study in the USA finding that smokers had six times the odds of developing RA compared to non-smokers.²⁵

The presentation and disease course are distinct for each patient, making diagnosis and management a complex and dynamic process. There is significant morbidity and mortality. Chronic systemic inflammation also contributes significantly to excess cardiovascular disease.

The typical case of RA begins insidiously, with the slow development of signs and symptoms over weeks to months. Stiffness, usually accompanied by pain on movement and by tenderness in the joint, is usually the first symptom.²⁶ Early diagnosis and management of RA presents an important opportunity to alter the course of this progressive disease. There is a window of opportunity within the first few months of disease onset to provide treatment that effectively limits structural damage and improves health outcomes.²⁷

Clinical features

The onset of RA may be insidious or acute. Typically, patients present with a symmetrical arthritis affecting the wrists and the metacarpophalangeal and proximal interphalangeal joints of the hands. Involvement of the metatarsophalangeal joints of the feet is also common. Occasionally, large joints can be affected in isolation, in which case sepsis or crystal arthropathy may need to be excluded.

The number of swollen or tender joints at baseline is an indicator of progressive disease and future radiographic progression.²⁸

A cardinal feature of RA is early morning stiffness, which can last for over 1 hour. Systemic features include flu-like symptoms, fatigue, malaise and weight loss. Rheumatoid nodules, commonly appearing over the extensor aspect of the elbows, are a specific feature but occur late in the disease and are only seen in 30% of patients. An important variation from this typical presentation is the so-called 'polymyalgic' onset of RA, a pattern occasionally seen in individuals over 65 years of age. These patients present with limb girdle pain rather than peripheral arthritis and have prominent stiffness.²⁹

Investigations

Inflammatory markers

Erythrocyte sedimentation rate and C-reactive protein are usually elevated at diagnosis. They are of benefit in monitoring disease activity and response to treatment.³⁰

Rheumatoid factor

Rheumatoid factor (RhF) is an auto-antibody against the Fc portion of immunoglobulin G (IgG). It is positive in 60–70% of RA patients but also occurs in chronic inflammatory diseases such as systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), Sjogren syndrome and cryoglobulinaemia. In the Presence of RA it indicates more aggressive disease.³⁰

Anticyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies

Anti-CCP antibodies are a relatively new test that has a similar sensitivity but higher specificity for RA than RhF. It is a strong predictor of erosive disease. Testing for the combination of anti-CCP antibodies and RhF may be better than either antibody alone^[30]

Plain X-rays

Plain films of the hand and feet demonstrate erosions, although these may not be present at

baseline. Serial X-rays every 1–2 years identify disease progression.³⁰

Table 1: Differential diagnosis for RA.

S.No.	Diagnosis for RA	
1.	Infective arthritis	Septic (bacterial) arthritis b. Acute polyarthrits (parvovirus, Ross River virus, Barmah Forrest virus)
2.	Reactive arthritis	
3.	Psoriatic arthritis	
4.	Crystal arthritis	

Current treatment options available

Simple analgesia and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs

Paracetamol patients with RA ultimately require DMARD therapy but adequate analgesia is also important. Remains the analgesic of choice given its excellent safety profile and is prescribed in regular divided doses to a maximum of 4 g/day. Alone, however, it may provide insufficient pain relief.³¹

If NSAIDs or COX-2 inhibitors are used, they should be used at the lowest effective dose and for the shortest possible duration. The addition of a proton pump inhibitor can reduce the incidence of gastrointestinal bleeding. Given concerns about the increased risk of cardiac and cerebrovascular events with both conventional NSAIDs and COX-2 inhibitors, they should be used only after careful evaluation of cardiovascular status and avoided in high risk individuals.³²

Omega-3 supplementation

Omega-3 fatty acid supplementation may be an effective adjunctive treatment. This was demonstrated in a meta-analysis of 17 randomised controlled trials involving a total of 823 patients, which showed a significant beneficial effect on pain, morning stiffness,

number of painful and/or tender joints and NSAID consumption.³³

Corticosteroids

In patients for whom simple analgesia and NSAID therapy is inadequate, oral corticosteroids are sometimes appropriate while awaiting rheumatology review.³³

General practitioners should consider short term, low dose, oral corticosteroid treatment when simple analgesics, omega- 3 fatty acids, and NSAIDs or COX-2 inhibitors have failed to achieve symptomatic relief. This should be undertaken in consultation with a rheumatologist, and with a consideration of the patient’s comorbidities and individual risk factors.³⁴

Disease modifying antirheumatic drugs

There have been significant changes in the approach to the management of RA since the mid 1990s. These include earlier and more aggressive intervention with DMARDs, combination DMARD therapy, and the introduction of biologic therapy for those who fail conventional DMARDs. Disease modifying antirheumatic drugs reduce the rate of erosive change and therefore have the potential to alter disease course by preventing irreversible damage (Table 2). Multiple international guidelines recommend that patients be commenced on DMARD therapy as soon as possible after a diagnosis of RA is established. Methotrexate (MTX) is now the most commonly used first line DMARD because of its efficacy, favourable toxicity profile, and low cost^[35]. It is dosed weekly, usually together with folic acid supplementation to reduce potential side effects. It is usually administered orally but can be given subcutaneously, particularly when poor oral absorption is suspected. Regular monitoring of FBC, renal function and LFTs is required, usually every 2–3 months once stable. Adverse effects of MTX include bone marrow suppression, liver damage and lung disease. Patients should be advised to avoid alcohol due to the increased risk of cirrhosis. Because of the potential toxicities of these agents, DMARD therapy should be initiated by a rheumatologist.

If this is not possible, the general practitioner should consider commencing single drug therapy with MTX or sulfasalazine in consultation with a rheumatologist.^{35,36}

Table 2: Common DMARDs in present.

S.No.	Traditional	Biologic
1.	Methotrexate	Adalimumab
2.	Sulfasalazine	Etanercept
3.	Hydroxychloroquine	Infliximab
4.	Leflunomide	Rituximab
5.	-----	Abatacept

Current treatment of patients with undifferentiated inflammatory arthritis consists primarily of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and cyclo-oxygenase-2 selective (COX-2) inhibitors. These medications have both analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects in RA; however, there is no evidence that they prevent joint damage.^{36,37}

In some studies, methotrexate (MTX) treatment has resulted in postponing the diagnosis of RA and retarding radiographic joint damage in undifferentiated inflammatory arthritis patients.³⁸ It is now well accepted that patients who are most likely to develop disabling arthritis should start DMARD therapy as soon as possible.³⁹

When patients start DMARD therapy early, they experience reduced radiographic joint damage and greater maintenance of function compared with patients whose treatment is delayed.^{38,40,41}

Historical perspective

Some of the most effective treatments against arthritis have been the anti-inflammatories known as glucocorticoids that have been in use for about 50 years.⁴² However, the disease itself began having its histological and molecular characteristics investigated systematically only from the mid-1960s onward. For example, electron microscopic studies of tissues in RA began showing in detail the extent of tissue damage in joints, but also corollary effects such as angiopathies.⁴³ Serological analyses in the late 1960s focused on developing correlations between the disease and known

macromolecules, such as the deficiency in I-A-globulin that occurs sometimes in RA.⁴⁴ These analyses were complemented by studies that focused on the effects of medications used at the time, such as anti-inflammatories, on joint or synovial tissue. At the same time, initial efforts toward hip surgery, including endoprosthesis, were also being developed.⁴⁵

The early 1970s saw the development of cell cultures from rheumatic tissues that would later form the basis of *in vitro* assays used for drug discovery,⁴⁶ as well as the application of nonsteroid and non-anti-inflammatory drugs in RA treatment, such as therapy using gold suspensions, which is used even today.⁴⁷ Later came the initial characterizations of autoantibodies against ubiquitous tissue antigens in RA.⁴⁸

Diagnostics based on bone density measurements began to be validated in the case of postmenopausal osteoarthritis in the mid-1980s,⁴⁹ heralding the growing importance of diagnostic monitoring that aims to begin treatment as early as possible. There were also increasing efforts to characterize the cytotoxic T-cell response in arthritis, based initially on correlations with viral infections, such as Epstein-Barr infection.⁵⁰

Current state

Key to the development of current therapies is the characterization of the variety of self-antigens that are the focus of the immune response. This is the subject of concerted efforts by many academic and corporate groups. One example of a recent auto antigen implicated in the disease is leukocyte function-associated antigen (LFA-1) in treatment-resistant Lyme arthritis.⁵¹

Reducing inflammation is the most commonly used treatment option in arthritis, and glucocorticosteroids, such as prednisolone and methylprednisolone, are some typical choices. However, there is still much that is uncertain about their real efficacy and tolerance profiles, even though they have been in use for some time.⁵² At present, a great deal of attention is

being focused on nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) based on inhibiting the cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes. The two isoforms, COX-1 and COX-2, are central to the production of prostaglandins, produced in excess at sites of inflammation. COX-1 synthesizes prostaglandins that are involved in the regulation of normal cell activity, whereas COX-2 produces prostaglandins mainly where inflammation occurs.⁵³ Finally, there is emerging recognition that synovial tissues in arthritis may be under attack not just from antibodies or cytotoxic T-cells that recognize self-antigens, but also from the complement system. This critical molecular cascade goes awry in a number of conditions, including arthritis, and is the subject of intense research and development.⁵⁴

Five tips for living with arthritis

1. *Get educated:* know the type of arthritis you have and the treatments available.
2. *Stay involved:* be an active participant in decisions about your care.
3. *Know your resources:* know where to get the support and resources you need.
4. *Stay healthy:* exercise regularly, eat a balanced healthy diet, and maintain a healthy weight.
5. *Know your medications:* tell your health care provider about all of the prescription and non-prescription medications you are taking.⁵⁴

Principle of drug management

Successful treatment to limit joint damage and functional loss requires early diagnosis, timely initiation of disease modifying agents, and provision of multidisciplinary support to manage the physical, social, emotional and occupational impact. The ultimate aim in treating RA is to induce complete remission. If remission is unable to be achieved, treatment aims to control disease activity and slow the rate of joint damage.⁵⁵ Other treatment goals include alleviation of pain, maintenance of function for essential activities of daily living (ADL) and

work, and maximisation of quality of life. In one recent study, more than three quarters of patients treated with a combination of etanercept and methotrexate experienced no progression of joint damage after 3 years of treatment.⁵⁶ In a separate study of a biologic used alone as a first-line therapy, approximately half the subjects receiving abatacept had a clinically and statistically significant reduction in signs and symptoms of RA over 6 months, accompanied by improvement in physical function.⁵⁷

Biotechnology in RA treatment

Biotech drugs work faster with fewer systemic side effects than earlier treatments. Most importantly, these drugs address the underlying biological cause of inflammation and tissue destruction. With the introduction of the first biologic RA therapies — tumor necrosis factor (TNF) blockers etanercept, adalimumab, and infliximab, and also anakinra, an interleukin-1 receptor antagonist — the treatment of RA changed drastically. Approved by the FDA last December, abatacept was the first of these new-generation RA biologics to reach the marketplace. Abatacept, which is indicated for patients who have failed one or more DMARDs or TNF inhibitors, takes an approach that differs from the TNF inhibitors. A recombinant fusion protein, abatacept prevents a cascade that results in full activation of T cells. This agent has been shown to be effective in reducing joint destruction and in improving signs and symptoms of RA in patients that have an inadequate response to TNF blockers. In a recent study, the abatacept group showed significant improvement in all eight physical and mental subscales of the Short Form (SF-36) Health Survey.⁵⁸ Approved by the FDA for use in RA patients on February 28, rituximab's mechanism of action may affect a number of pathways by which B-cells are thought to contribute to the genesis and development of RA.⁵⁸

Clinical progress

Arthritis is the subject of numerous clinical trials investigating new agents or ones already in use for side effects. For example, even though Celebrex (celecoxib) is prescribed, clinical trials

are ongoing to refine its side-effect profile and determine additional uses. For example, a recent report describes the effects of the drug on the gastrointestinal mucosal surface, and on platelet function in comparison to naproxen, a COX-1 inhibiting NSAID.⁵⁹ The small-scale trials showed that no ulcers occurred in patients receiving celecoxib in comparison to 19% of patients who received naproxen. Also, there was no statistically significant effect on platelet aggregation or bleeding time with celecoxib, whereas such effects were observed with naproxen. The results of these trials confirm the advantage of COX-2 selectivity in terms of reducing side effects in arthritis treatment. Indeed, COX-2 is the target for several inhibitors, in addition to celecoxib, that are under development with the goal of improving efficacy and reducing side effects.⁶⁰ In addition to single-drug clinical trials focusing on new targets, there are other trials that aim to optimize current approaches, specifically comparing various regimens of combination therapy in arthritis. One recent trial involved 199 patients in a multicenter, randomized study with a two-year follow-up, comparing combination therapy (sulfasalazine, methotrexate, hydroxychloroquine, and prednisolone) with a single antirheumatic drug (sulfasalazine or methotrexate) with or without prednisolone, in early RA.⁶¹ Finally, other types of trials aim to determine the effects of antiarthritis drugs on various molecular responses, such as the production and subsequent effect of cytokines. For example, a recent trial linked the immune suppressive effect of dexamethasone on interleukin-10 (IL-10) production and on the type 1 (T1)/type 2 (T2) T-cell balance found in RA.⁶²

Industry challenges

Several hypotheses can offer some insight, and some interesting approaches are emerging that attempt to enhance our understanding of the underlying causes, thus helping to design better drugs. For example, recent work focuses on gene variations that they correlate with arthritis. A good example is the variation observed in the estrogen receptor gene that has been linked to

the age of onset of RA in women, but not in men^[63].

Increasing understanding of this process has led to the validation of MMPs as targets for the development of inhibitors and has prompted efforts aimed at finding out why the inhibitors went out of balance in the first place. With respect to MMP inhibitors, there has been considerable progress recently in obtaining three-dimensional structures of the enzymes alone and in combination with their inhibitors, which will help in the design of novel inhibitors with clinical potential.⁶⁴

Drugs in pipeline

The FDA approvals of abatacept and rituximab are the first of what may be several novel autoimmune and anti-inflammatory biotech agents to reach the marketplace in the not-too-distant future. There is significant activity in the pipeline spanning new biological pathways, new molecules, and additional indications for current drugs. In the RA field alone, current activity includes the following:

Tacrolimus (Prograf) is an immunosuppressant that is presently used in organ transplant patients. Like abatacept, tacrolimus acts on T cells by preventing their activation and has been tested in RA patients that have not responded to DMARDs.⁶⁵ In a study intended to evaluate the long-term safety of tacrolimus in patients with RA, 38 percent of patients receiving at least 3 mg per day achieved an ACR 20 response rate.⁶⁶

Bristol-Myers Squibb, developer of the costimulation blocker abatacept, is working on another — belatacept — which is derived from abatacept.⁶⁷ As research continues into immunology, other targets are being discovered to block the inflammation process. Interleukin-6 is a protein that is overproduced in the joints of people with RA and may be a cause of fever and excess blood platelets in these patients.⁶⁵ Clinical trials of tocilizumab (Actemra), a humanized anti-human IL-6 receptor monoclonal antibody, are underway in Japan. In a phase 3 trial in adults, the primary endpoint is ACR 20 improvement; a phase 2 trial is being conducted for JRA.⁶⁸

New therapeutic targets launched

Many emerging biologic treatments are aimed at simplifying dosing, decreasing adverse events, and improving efficacy in the treatment of RA. Proinflammatory cytokines such as interleukin (IL)-1 beta, IL-6, and IL-17 look the most promising as targets for new monoclonal antibodies. These agents work by neutralizing a cytokine or its receptor, blocking costimulation molecule signaling, and inducing osmotic cell lysis, apoptosis, or depletion of target-cell molecules. The other target of therapy is small molecules with molecular weights less than 1 kDa. These agents are expected to have at least the same efficacy as current biologics and, due to their oral administration, may have fewer side effects and be less expensive.⁶⁹

Monoclonal antibodies: inhibitors of proinflammatory cytokines

Canakinumab is a fully human anti-IL-1 beta monoclonal antibody currently FDA approved for treatment of cryopyrin-associated periodic syndromes (CAPS). It is now being investigated for RA in phase 2 and phase 3 trials.¹¹ It is hoped that canakinumab will be found more effective than anakinra due to a greater affinity to IL-1. Gevokizumab is another humanized anti-IL-1 beta monoclonal antibody being investigated for many autoinflammatory conditions including RA. Data from preclinical trials showed that it may be effective and well tolerated; however, the only phase 2 study for RA with this agent was suspended at the end of May 2011.⁷⁰

Similar to tocilizumab, which is now on the market and targets IL-6 receptors, sirukumab is a human anti-IL-6 monoclonal antibody; 2 phase 2 studies of sirukumab are planned for patients with RA. Initial reports from a phase 2 dose-finding study look promising, with patients currently taking MTX receiving sirukumab 100 mg SC every 2 weeks or placebo. By week 12, a 20% improvement in ACR 20 was seen in 75% of patients taking sirukumab compared to 21% of patients taking placebo ($P=.002$) and treatment was well tolerated.⁷¹

IL-17 increases the production of many inflammatory cytokines and regulates the development of osteoclasts.⁶⁹

Secukinumab is a human anti-IL-17A monoclonal antibody currently under phase 3 development for multiple diseases, including RA. Two phase 2 studies have been published to date. The first study completed in 2010 included patients with psoriasis, RA, and chronic noninfectious uveitis. Adverse event rates were similar between treatment and placebo; the most frequently observed nonserious infections were URT infection and nasopharyngitis. Another randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase 2 study was published in 2012. Patients with an inadequate response to MTX were assigned to receive monthly injections of secukinumab 25 mg, 75 mg, 150 mg, 300 mg, or placebo. The primary endpoint of ACR 20 response at week 16 was not achieved; however, a trend toward benefit was observed. Response rates compared to placebo were 34%, 46.9%, 46.5%, and 53.7% versus 36%, respectively. Overall safety was comparable between dosage groups and placebo. Consistent with the previous study, infections were most commonly nasopharyngitis, URT infection, pharyngitis, sinusitis, and urinary-tract infection.

T cells and B cells

B cells produce cytokines and present self antigens to T cells. B-cell depletion therapy seems like a reasonable therapeutic target in RA because B cells and their autoantibodies may have a self-perpetuation cycle that does not require T-cell activity. Considering the positive effect seen with rituximab (an anti-CD20 currently on the market) in B-cell depletion, other medications are in the pipeline to target this pathway. Ofatumumab is a human anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody that was FDA approved in 2009 for the treatment of chronic lymphocytic leukemia. It is currently under phase 3 development for RA. It targets a different CD20 epitope than that targeted by rituximab and ocrelizumab, and has looked promising in animal studies.⁷¹

Results from 2 human trials have currently been published, and others are in progress. The

manufacturers will focus development on an SC formulation of the drug instead of IV infusions for greater patient convenience. Two severe adverse events in the ofatumumab group (angioedema and pneumonia) were considered to be drug related.⁷²

Veltuzumab is another humanized anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody that will be delivered by SC injection. It is currently in a phase 2, dose-finding study (VELVET, or Veltuzumab Various Doses Exploratory Trial), which has been put on hold temporarily until new drug is available in the second half of 2012. This trial is studying patients with moderate-to-severe RA that is not controlled using MTX or MTX plus anti-TNF therapy. Development for ocrelizumab, another humanized anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody, has been suspended by its manufacturer after a data and safety monitoring board decided that the safety risk of opportunistic infections outweighed the benefits seen in patients with RA. The drug will continue to be developed for relapsing remitting multiple sclerosis. A human monoclonal anti-B lymphocyte stimulator (BLyS) antibody, belimumab, is currently FDA approved for use in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus and has completed a phase 2 study in patients with RA. This study did not find a statistically significant difference in the percentage of patients who achieved an ACR 20 response at 24 weeks at higher doses of belimumab (4 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg compared to placebo) but did find a statistical improvement with the lower dose (1 mg/kg). Atacicept is a recombinant fusion protein that neutralizes the B-cell maturation/survival factors B-lymphocyte stimulator (BLyS) and APRIL, a proliferation-inducing ligand. Both BLyS and APRIL have been shown to be elevated in patients with RA, and it has been hypothesized that atacicept may have better results than belimumab due to targeting APRIL in addition to BLyS. Two phase 2, multicenter, randomized, controlled trials—Atacicept for Reduction of Signs and Symptoms in the RA Trial (AUGUST) I and AUGUST II—were conducted in patients with an inadequate response to TNF antagonist therapy or MTX, respectively [^{73,74}]. Despite improvement in immunoglobulin and RF levels,

the primary endpoints of response according to ACR 20 using C-reactive protein (CRP) levels did not differ between the atacept groups and placebo. No treatment-related adverse events were of concern and atacept appeared safe.⁷³⁻⁷⁵

Denosumab is a monoclonal antibody that inhibits osteoclastogenesis by its activity against receptor activator for nuclear factor kappa-B ligand (RANKL). It is currently FDA approved for the treatment of osteoporosis, cancer treatment-induced bone loss, and solid tumor-associated bone metastases. Four phase 2 studies have been published to examine denosumab's effect on bone erosions and osteoporosis. In patients with RA taking MTX, denosumab 60 to 180 mg SC administered at baseline and at 6 months provided protection against bone loss; increased hand, metacarpal, spine, and hip bone mineral density; and decreased erosion seen by magnetic resonance imaging. Rates of adverse events were comparable between treatment and placebo groups.⁷⁶⁻⁷⁸

Small molecules to be targeted

Inhibitors of intracellular signaling molecules

The p38-alpha mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) has been a target for development because this enzyme is important to the signaling pathway for the generation of TNF alpha or IL-1 beta. Pamapimod selectively inhibits the alpha isoform of p38 MAPK, but it appears to be less effective than MTX or placebo for patients with RA after 12 weeks of study.^{79,80} Despite promising preclinical results, such MAPK inhibitors have shown poor clinical response.⁸¹

Tofacitinib (formerly tasocitinib) was recommended for approval by the Arthritis Advisory Committee to the FDA in May 2012. If approved, this will be the first RA treatment in a new class of medications known as Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors. Tofacitinib is an orally administered JAK inhibitor that selectively inhibits JAK-1, JAK-2, and JAK-3 in vitro. JAKs are central to immune cell activity, cytokine activation, and signaling. In 12 weeks, doses of tofacitinib of 3 mg or greater twice daily were associated with a 50.7% to 58.1%

response rate in ACR 20, which was significantly greater than placebo at 33.3% in patients already taking MTX ($P=0.05$). Adverse effects that occurred in more than 10% of patients included diarrhea, URT infection, and headache.⁸²

A second study was conducted in a Japanese population taking MTX and found ACR 20 responses at 12 weeks of 64.3% with 1 mg twice daily, 77.8% with 3 mg twice daily, 96.3% with 5 mg twice daily, and 80.8% with 10 mg twice daily, versus placebo at 14.3% ($P<.0001$).⁴¹ Both studies found some incidence of elevated liver enzymes.^{82,83} Spleen tyrosine kinase (Syk) inhibitors are also being investigated. The Syk signaling pathway is upstream of MAP kinases and its activation plays an important role in the TNF alpha-induced expression of inflammatory cytokines. Fostamatinib is an oral Syk inhibitor that has shown benefit in 2 phase 2 trials.^{84,85}

Phase 3 trials of the agent are currently under way. Doses of 100 mg twice daily and 150 mg once daily were significantly better than placebo at 6 months (ACR 20 response rates of 67% and 57%, respectively, vs 35%; $P<0.001$).⁹³ Doses of 100 mg twice daily and 150 mg twice daily were also significantly better than placebo or doses of 50 mg twice daily at 12 weeks (ACR 20 response rates of 65% and 72% vs 38% and 32%, respectively; $P<0.01$).⁸⁴

Diarrhea, URT infection, neutropenia, increased blood pressure, and elevated liver enzymes were most commonly associated with the higher doses of fostamatinib.^{84,85} The most recent study of fostamatinib did not find a difference in ACR 20 response at 3 months in the 100-mg twice-daily group compared to placebo in patients who had failed biologic treatment.⁸⁶

Inhibitor of cytokines and chemokines

Apilimod is an oral inhibitor of IL-12 and IL-23 in which the exact mechanism of the inhibition is unknown. A phase 2 study of patients also taking MTX revealed that apilimod is not a likely candidate for further development, because ACR 20 response was similar to

placebo and all patients in the treatment group experienced headache or nausea.⁸⁷

PDE4 inhibitor

Apremilast is an oral phosphodiesterase type 4 inhibitor (PDE4) currently being developed to treat inflammatory disorders. PDE4 inhibits proinflammatory cytokines by causing an accumulation of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP). Protein kinase A is activated by cAMP. Although there are no clinical data thus far, preclinical data look promising and recruitment for phase 2 studies is ongoing^[88].

Future directions

Future efforts against arthritis will center on the identification of what causes the immune system go away, and also the identification of candidate self-antigens targeted in arthritis. Ongoing research will be helped by animal studies and in vitro models of arthritis based on tissue culture of rheumatoid synovial fibroblasts. The latter are being used increasingly to study specific signal transduction mechanisms in the disease. It was found recently that once the thrombin receptor is activated in these cells, they subsequently produce interleukin-6 and granulocyte colony-stimulating factor, both of which lead to inflammation.⁸⁹

In the future, increasing attention will be directed toward by-products of molecular events that have gone wrong in arthritis and on their synergistic effect in promoting the disease. A good example, nitric oxide, is produced in excess in rheumatoid tissues and is now being investigated for its effects in cartilage damage in arthritic joints.⁹⁰ Another good example is tumor necrosis factor (TNF), an inflammation-promoting cytokine associated with multiple inflammatory events, including arthritis. Anti-TNF therapies are the subject of intense research, and first-generation therapies are already on the market.⁹¹

Although a lot is already known about certain molecular pathways involved in specific aspects of arthritis, as well as the effects of drugs, the future will see increased efforts to refine our

understanding of the mode of action of new drugs. Hopefully, this will lead to the design of even better drugs with more specific benefits and fewer side effects. For example, a recent study reports on the novel actions of the NSAID aceclofenac, prescribed for RA and osteoarthritis. The study showed that the therapeutic effects of aceclofenac are due, to a certain degree, to a newly described chondroprotective effect of a metabolite of the drug, which suppresses promatrix metalloproteinase production and proteoglycan release and therefore reduces arthritic symptoms^[92]. This and other studies of this type on mode of action issues will no doubt lead to optimized drug design efforts as well as to the validation of novel targets for de novo drug design, via the elucidation of specific pathways involved in the disease. Specific examples of novel targets for anti-arthritis drugs include vascular adhesion protein-1 (VAP-1), which mediates leukocyte-endothelial cell interactions and can also be used as a potential target for imaging inflammation itself,⁹³ vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) isoforms and VEGF receptors, Flt-1, KDR and neuropilin-1, all of which are involved in angiogenesis which itself is central to the development of RA.⁹⁴

It should also be pointed out that diagnostic methods for arthritis continue to improve and evolve. For example, a recent study shows how synovial fluid has certain physical characteristics that enable the distinction between inflammatory and degenerative arthritis using non-invasive analysis by spin echo diffusion, which is an analytical method for determining flow characteristics and differences among viscous fluids. This observation can potentially lead to a better prediction of the nature of arthritis early on in patients who have inflamed joints.⁹⁵

Finally, the future will also see the increasing application of gene therapy as a front-line defense against the disease, aiming at long-term corrective treatment. A variety of genes that code for antiarthritic proteins are under investigation, including IL-1Ra, IL-1sR, TNFsR, transforming growth factor (TGF), IL-13, Fas L, IL-10, and vIL-10, as are the vectors that will carry them to arthritic tissues.

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